

Chemical and Microbiological Studies on some [Ni(amine)_n]²⁺(WO₄²⁻) Complexes

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Manuscript received 12 November 1985, revised 7 May 1986, accepted 8 June 1986

Some structural findings on the complexes of the type [Ni^{II}(amine)_n]²⁺(WO₄²⁻) are reported. The probable structures have been worked out on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility, visible and infrared spectral data. The octahedral complexes showed a characteristic X-ray powder diffraction pattern. The unit cell for complex tris(1,2-diaminoethane)nickel(II) tungstate complex was found to be primitive cubic type with lattice constants $a=b=c=14.098 \text{ \AA}$. Antibacterial activity of these complexes have been studied for *Salmonella typhi*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Styphlococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas mangiferae*.

In our previous papers, we have communicated some structural aspects of Ni^{II} complexes having 2-pyrrolidonate anion^{1,2}. These complexes have shown remarkable antifungal activity against *Botryodiplodia theobromae* (apple strain). The aim of present investigations is to study the coordination behaviour of Ni^{II} in octahedral field in presence of a different anion. We have noted that there are certain changes in the properties of such complexes in presence of WO₄²⁻ anion. Three complexes with 1,2-diamino ethane (en), 1,2-diaminopropane (pn) and diethylenetriamine (dien) have been isolated and characterised.

Experimental

NiWO₄·3H₂O was prepared by the method reported in the literature³ and its purity was checked by estimation of Ni and W. The [Ni-(amine)_n]²⁺(WO₄²⁻) complexes were isolated by shaking NiWO₄·3H₂O (0.01 mol) with the required amine (0.03 mol) in acetone (~100 ml). The complexation was marked by change in colour from green to violet/purple. The products were filtered, washed 3-4 times with acetone and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀ before analysis. Ni and W in the complexes were determined gravimetrically as bis-glyoximatonicel(II) and barium tungstate, respectively^{4,5}. C, H and N were

analysed at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Ir spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes were determined by Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the standard. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The results are presented in the Tables 1-5. The X-ray powder pattern was recorded on a diffractometer attached Phillips X-ray machine using CuK_α 1.541 8 Å radiation at the University of Aberdeen, Scotland, U. K.

Toxicity study : Toxicity study of the complexes was made against four pathogenic bacteria, viz. *Salmonella typhi*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Styphlococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas mangiferae*. Antibacterial activity of complexes was determined by standard paper disc method of Raper *et al.*⁶. Complexes were first sterilised with ethanol, dried and redissolved in sterilised water under aseptic conditions. Sterilised filter paper disc (6 mm) were dipped into the complex solutions of different concentrations, 0.01, 0.05 and 0.1 M. Prior to this, the bacteria being homogenised with nutrient agar media (at 30-35°) were plated into the sterilised petri dishes. Dipped filter paper discs were placed on seeded medium. After 24 h of incubation, the antibacterial activities were recorded by measuring the inhibition zone against various complexes.

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS, MAGNETIC AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF Ni^{II}(AMINE)_nWO₄ COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} (at 298 K) B.M.	Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		Ni	N	W		
Ni(C ₂ H ₈ N ₂) ₃ WO ₄	Violet	12.17 (12.09)	17.91 (17.25)	37.46 (37.60)	3.14	249
Ni(C ₂ H ₁₀ N ₂) ₃ WO ₄	Purple	11.27 (11.10)	15.34 (15.87)	34.48 (34.61)	3.15	230
Ni(C ₂ H ₁₁ N ₃) ₃ WO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	Purple	10.52 (10.69)	15.12 (15.30)	34.00 (33.30)	3.40	221

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS (IN cm^{-1}) OF Ni^{II} (AMINE) $_n\text{WO}_4$ COMPLEXES

Compd.	Observed band and assignment			Ligand field parameters		
	${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$	${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$	${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$	Dq	B	β
$\text{Ni(en)}_3\text{WO}_4$	12 500	18 170	29 000	1 250	677	0.63
$\text{Ni(pn)}_3\text{WO}_4$	12 880	18 180	29 410	1 288	646	0.60
$\text{Ni(dien)}_3\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	13 050	18 760	29 850	1 305	660	0.61

 TABLE 3—PRINCIPAL INFRARED SPECTRAL BAND* (cm^{-1}) AND ASSIGNMENT OF Ni (AMINE) $_n\text{WO}_4$ COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_{OH}	$\nu_{\text{N-H}}$	$\delta_{\text{O-H}}$	$\delta_{\text{N-H}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{W-O}}$	$\gamma_{\text{N-H}}$	$\nu_{\text{Ni-N}}$
en	—	3 330vs 3 260vs 3 165s	—	1 590vs	1 040s	—	820vs	—
$\text{Ni(en)}_3\text{WO}_4$	—	3 295vs 3 220vs 3 130vs	—	1 586s	1 025s	970sh 845w	810s	515s
pn	—	3 335vs 3 260vs 3 160s	—	1 590vs	1 130m	—	840s	—
$\text{Ni(pn)}_3\text{WO}_4$	—	3 250vs — 3 130vs	—	1 588vs	1 076s	931s 820s	805s	525s
dien	—	3 340vs 3 250vs 3 160ms	—	1 590vs	1 117ms	—	830s	—
$\text{Ni(dien)}_3\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3 440—3 340br	3 250vs — 3 156vs	1 625m	1 560m	1 080s	973vs 835w	820vs	512s

* s=sharp, vs=very sharp, m=medium, br=broad, w=weak.

Streptomycin solution (40 mg ml^{-1}) was taken as the control.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of elemental analysis the molecular formula of the complexes work out to be NiL_3WO_4 for $L=\text{en}$, pn , and $\text{NiL}_3\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for $L=\text{dien}$. Their magnetic moment values lie in the range 3.14–3.41 B.M. which are in good agreement with the reported values of Ni^{II} complexes in octahedral field (2.92–3.41 B.M.) corresponding to two unpaired electrons^{7,8}. The molar conductance values ($221\text{--}249 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate the ionic nature of these complexes, $[\text{Ni}(\text{amine})_n]^{2+} (\text{WO}_4^{2-})$ where $n=2, 3$ (Ref. 9).

The electronic spectra of the complexes show three prominent bands (Table 2). The band positions suggest the octahedral geometry of the six-coordinate complexes^{10,11}. The ligand field parameters B , β and Dq are shown in the Table 2. The B values vary from $646\text{--}677 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Racah parameter values have been found to be about 60–63% of the free ion value ($1 080 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)¹². This could be due to distortion of the 'Oh' symmetry in the aqueous solutions of the complexes.

Some relevant ir bands of the complexes presented in Table 3 along with their tentative assignments^{13,14}. A negative shift in N–H stretching has been noted in all the amine complexes. The negative shift of $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ band of the amines indicate Ni–N bonding¹⁵. The dien complex,

$[\text{Ni}(\text{dien})_3]\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows a broad band ($3 500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and a sharp band ($1 625 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicating the presence of water of crystallisation^{16,17}. The ir bands due to the oxoanion¹⁸ WO_4^{2-} in these complexes were identified at $800\text{--}1 000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The $\nu_{\text{Ni-N}}$ were observed in the region $550\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Ref. 19).

Table 4 reveals the X-ray powder diffraction data on tris(1,2-diaminoethane)nickel(II) tungstate. The diffraction pattern consists of 17 reflections

 TABLE 4—POWDER DIFFRACTION DATA FOR $[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3]\text{WO}_4$ COMPLEX

Peak no.	2θ	Relative intensity $I/I_0 \times 100$	d Å	$\text{Sin}^2\theta / \text{C.F.}^*$	$(h^2+k^2+l^2)$	hkl
1.	10.7	7.9	8.267 8	2.90	3	(111)
2.	14.1	11	6.280 9	5.00	5	(210)
3.	17.4	100	5.096 4	7.95	8	(220)
4.	18.8	47	4.719 9	9.20	9	(221)
5.	20.8	18	4.270 4	10.898	11	(311)
6.	22.0	19	4.040 1	12.10	12	(222)
7.	23.7	29	3.754 0	14.10	14	(321)
8.	26.0	34	3.426 9	16.92	17	(322) (410)
9.	29.0	12	3.007 89	20.93	21	(421)
10.	31.0	6	2.884 7	23.89	24	(422)
11.	38.3	8	2.350 0	35.99	36	(600)
12.	41.1	11	2.196 1	41.00	41	(449) (540)
13.	43.1	8	2.098 7	45.10	45	(542)
14.	47.0	5	1.933 3	53.10	53	(641)
15.	52.3	6	1.749 1	64.97	65	(652)
16.	55.7	6	1.650 2	72.99	73	(830)
17.	59.0	6	1.565 5	81.09	81	(900)

* C.F.=Common factor=0.002 99.

TABLE 5—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF $[\text{Ni}(\text{AMINE})_2]\text{WO}_4$ COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

Strains of Bacteria	Zone of inhibition (mm)*									Control of streptomycin 40 mg ml ⁻¹
	Ni(en) ₂ WO ₄			Ni(pn) ₂ WO ₄			Ni(dien) ₂ WO ₄			
	0.01M	0.05M	0.1M	0.01M	0.05M	0.1M	0.01M	0.05M	0.1M	
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	9	15	20	7	8	20	11	15	18	22
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>	10	12	21	10	13	25	8	10	14	27
<i>Styphlococcus aureus</i>	9	19	29	8	10	26	7	9	15	25
<i>Pseudomonas mangiferae</i>	7	15	22	9	17	23	9	18	24	30

* Including diameter of filter paper disc (6 mm).

between 5–60° '2θ' values. The unit cell calculations have been done for cubic symmetry of the complex. The characteristic for the cubic system is that sin²θ values have a common factor. The cell parameter has been calculated by the equation for cubic system,

$a=b=c=(\lambda\sqrt{h^2+k^2+l^2})/2\sin\theta$, where, $\lambda/2a$ is the common factor. The experimental values of sin²θ/common factor are recorded for each peak in Table 5. The ($h^2+k^2+l^2$) values are 3,5,8,9,11,12,14,17,21,24,36,41,45,53,65,73 and 81. Absence of forbidden numbers confirms the cubic symmetry²⁰. The experimental values are in good agreement with ($h^2+k^2+l^2$) values²¹ of primitive type cubic cell with lattice constant $a=b=c=14.098\text{ \AA}$. The X-ray work on the other two compounds are in progress.

Microbial study indicate remarkable toxic effect of the complexes against all the four pathogenic bacteria. The $[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_2]\text{WO}_4$ complex was most toxic against *S. aureus* at 0.1 M concentration. A comparative study showed that the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{dien})_2]\text{WO}_4$ was the least toxic one against all the four pathogenic bacteria, but it was found to be active against *P. mangiferae* at higher concentration. At lower concentrations (0.01 M), all the complexes induced inhibition zone against *S. aureus*. The en, pn complexes were found to be more effective and induced almost 1.5–2 times inhibition than the dien complex in the cases of *P. mangiferae* and *B. pumilus*. *S. typhi* was suppressed almost equally by all the three compounds. In general, the increase in inhibition zone was recorded with increase in concentration of the compounds.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, for providing facilities, and to Prof. F. P. Glasser,

University of Aberdeen, Scotland, U.K. for the X-ray data. Thanks are also due to Mr. H. H. S. Tripathi, for his help in collecting the antimicrobial data, and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support.

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